

Inhibitory Risks of Nanoplastics on Glucose and Peptide Uptake: Molecular Docking Insights into SGLT1 and PePT1

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Abstract

Plastic pollution is increasing worldwide and this has caused nanoplastics (NPs), which are smaller than 100 nm, to spread in environmental systems. Because of their small size NPs can pass through the cell membrane and accumulate in different tissues. Nanoplastic exposure has been reported to be related to structural damage, inflammation and reduced nutrient absorption in intestinal tissue. It is also stated that NPs may negatively affect protein and carbohydrate metabolism and slow down digestion processes. The aim of this study is to investigate the molecular interactions and inhibitory potential of Polyethylene terephthalate NPs with SGLT1 and PePT1 transporter proteins which are responsible for glucose and peptide absorption in the small intestine. For this purpose, the molecular docking method was used. Molecular analyses show that PET nanoplastics may block the transport mechanism by occupying the substrate binding sites of both transporter proteins. The results showed that PET nanoplastics have a high binding affinity to the SGLT1 transporter ($\Delta G = -9.8$ kcal/mol; $K_i \approx 123$ nM) and a stronger inhibitory potential compared to PePT1 ($\Delta G = -7.4$ kcal/mol; $K_i \approx 5.96$ μ M).

Keywords: Nanoplastics, Nutrient absorption, Molecular docking

Introduction

Plastics are widely used in many areas of daily life, from industry to the healthcare sector, because they are cheap and easy to process. Global plastic production was about 2 million tons in 1950, but it reached about 460 million tons in 2019 (Geyer, Jambeck, & Law, 2017). This rapid increase in plastic production has led to the accumulation of plastic waste in the environment and the formation of smaller plastic particles. The term “microplastic” (MP) was first used to describe plastic particles smaller than 5 mm in ocean and coastal ecosystems (Thompson et al., 2004). Today, MPs have been found in many environments such as seas, rivers, soil, air, and food (Napper et al., 2020; Ziani et al., 2023). Nanoplastics (NPs), which are formed by the breakdown of microplastics and are defined as being smaller than 100 nm, have gained more attention in recent years (Nihart et al., 2025). Because of their small size, these particles can cross the cell membrane through endocytosis (Liu et al., 2021).

Humans can be exposed to MPs and NPs through different routes such as ingestion, inhalation, and skin contact (Kannan & Vimalkumar, 2021). It is estimated that humans consume about 0.1 to 5 grams of microplastics per week (Senathirajah et al., 2021). The literature reports that MPs and NPs exhibit widespread systemic distribution in the cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, respiratory, endocrine and urinary systems. The detection of these particles in vital organs such as the brain, kidneys and lungs clearly demonstrates that plastic derivatives can cross critical biological barriers, such as the blood–brain barrier and the blood–air barrier (Roslan et al., 2024; Nihart et al., 2025; Sofield, Anderton, & Gorecki, 2024). Studies on the gastrointestinal system have shown that MP exposure can damage intestinal tissue integrity, increase intestinal permeability,

and cause oxidative stress and epithelial cell damage (Liang et al., 2021; Gałęcka & Całka, 2024). It has also been shown that MPs negatively affect the digestion of lipids, starch, and proteins (Tan et al., 2020; O’Brien et al., 2021; de Guzman et al., 2023). In addition, MP exposure has been reported to cause dysbiosis in the gut microbiota and affect energy metabolism (Okamura et al., 2023; Deng et al., 2017). These findings suggest that MPs and NPs may have important effects on nutrient absorption; however, the molecular mechanisms of these effects are not yet fully understood (Jadhav et al., 2021).

Molecular docking is a method that calculates how ligands bind to target proteins and their binding affinity, and it is widely used in drug discovery and inhibitor design (Agu et al., 2023). It has also been used to study the interactions between nanoplastics and biomolecules (Azhagesan et al., 2024; Abdulrahman, 2025).

In the small intestine, nutrient absorption occurs through transporter proteins in enterocytes located on the apical surface of villi. Sodium/glucose cotransporter 1 (SGLT1) is an important transporter that carries glucose and galactose into the cell together with sodium ions, and it is highly expressed especially in the jejunum (Cui et al., 2023; Hirayama et al., 2007). The absorption of di- and tripeptides formed during protein digestion is carried out by the proton-dependent Peptide transporter 1 (PePT1) transporter (Killer et al., 2021). Possible interactions of these transporters with microplastics may have important effects on nutrient transport and intestinal barrier functions. In this study, SGLT1 and PePT1 were selected as target proteins, and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) nanoplastic, which has high human exposure, was used as the ligand (Roslan et al., 2024; Nihart et al., 2025). Current studies are mostly at the histological and physiological level, and the direct molecular in-

teractions of MPs and NPs with intestinal transporter proteins have not been sufficiently studied. In this study, the interaction of PET nanoplastics with SGLT1 and PePT1 transporters was analyzed using molecular docking, and it was aimed to understand the possible effects of nanoplastic exposure on intestinal health and nutrient absorption at the molecular level.

Method

1. Selection and Preparation of Target Proteins

In molecular docking analysis, the electron microscopy structures of SGLT1 (PDB ID: 7YNI) and PePT1 (PDB ID: 7PN1), which play a key role in nutrient absorption in the human small intestine, were used as target proteins. In line with the aim of the study, the outward-open conformations of the transporter proteins were preferred. These conformations (7PN1 and 7WMV) are the most suitable structures to simulate the entry of natural ligands (glucose or peptides) from the small intestinal lumen into the binding pocket on the apical side. The three-dimensional crystal structures of the selected proteins were downloaded from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) database (Figure 1).

Figure 1: 3D crystal structures of SGLT1 and PePT1 transporter proteins

The proteins were prepared for docking analysis using AutoDockTools-1.5.7 software (Morris et al., 2009). Ligands and HETATM atoms on the proteins were removed. Polar hydrogens were added to the proteins, and Gasteiger partial atomic charges were assigned to correctly calculate electrostatic interactions between atoms. Then, the proteins were converted into PDBQT format.

2. Ligand (Nanoplastic) Structure Selection and Preparation

As the ligand of the study, PET was preferred because it is one of the most common nanoplastic types found in the human body (Roslan et al., 2024; Nihart et al., 2025). In this context, a representative nanoplastic structure of PET was mod-

eled as an oligomer (3-mer) consisting of three monomer units, with a size that can fit into the protein binding pocket and correctly represent interactions (Figure 2). The use of oligomers is a commonly accepted method in protein-plastic interaction studies (Duru et al., 2023). The two-dimensional structure of the ligand was drawn using ChemDraw software and converted into PDB format using OpenBabel software (O'Boyle et al., 2011). The geometry of the ligand was optimized using Avogadro software, and energy minimization was performed with the MMFF94 force field (Hanwell et al., 2012). Polar hydrogens were added to the ligand, and Gasteiger partial atomic charges were assigned. Then, the ligand was converted into PDBQT format (Morris et al., 2009).

Figure 2: 3D structure of the ligand

3. Active Site Prediction and Grid Box Optimization

The binding regions of the target proteins were defined as the pockets where natural ligands (glucose, galactose, and di/tripeptides) physiologically bind. To identify these regions, amino acid residues reported in the literature and known to play critical roles in transporter function were taken as a basis. For SGLT1, amino acid residues surrounding the glucose-binding pocket and involved in the extracellular gating mechanism of the transporter were selected as the center of the binding site (Figures 3, 4, and 5) with the SGLT1-binding inhibitor LX2761 (Niu et al., 2022). For PePT1, amino acid residues surrounding the peptide-binding pocket and contributing to the extracellular gating mechanism were used to define the active site (Figures 6 and 7). These residues are critical for substrate positioning and conformational changes of the protein during the transition from the outward-open to the inward-occluded conformation. Ensuring that the grid box encompasses these key residues and the transition pathway allowed the investigation of the potential for nanoplastics to disrupt the transport cycle by either mimicking glucose/peptide binding or physically blocking gate closure. Accordingly, the grid box dimensions were set to 50 Å, and the center coordinates were determined separately for SGLT1 and PePT1 using AutoDockTools-1.5.7 (Table 1) (Morris et al., 2009).

4. Molecular Docking Analysis

Molecular Docking analysis was performed using AutoDock Vina (Trott et al., 2010). Docking was carried out separately

Figure 3: Critical amino acids (T460, T156, Q457, I456, F453) and helices (TM1, TM2, TM3, TM10, TM6a) in the glucose-binding site of SGLT1 (Cui et al., 2022)

Figure 5: Critical amino acid residues (Q457, D454, T90, I98, L87, F101, H83, E102, A105, K321, T460, F453) and transmembrane helices (TM1a, TM1b, TM2, TM7, TM10) involved in interactions

Figure 4: Critical amino acids (Q457, I98, F101, M283, F453) and helices (TM1a, TM1b, TM2, TM10a) in the glucose-binding site of SGLT1 (Cui et al., 2022)

Protein	Center Coordinates (x,y,z)	Grid Box Dimensions (x,y,z)
<i>SGLT1</i>	101.542, 111.401, 113.654	50, 50, 50
<i>PePT1</i>	100.690, 107.895, 108.050	50, 50, 50

Table 1: Grid box parameters

Figure 6: Critical amino acids in the binding pocket of PePT1 (W293, V626, W622, Y64, L623, K140, R27, N329, E595, F297) (Killer et al., 2021)

Figure 7: Amino acids and salt bridges responsible for the stabilization and conformational changes (Killer et al., 2021)

each protein, and the docking parameters are listed in Table 2. The resulting protein-ligand complexes were analyzed in 3D using BIOVIA Discovery Studio (Dassault Systemes BIOVIA, 2025).

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>SGLT1</i>	<i>PePT1</i>
Grid box		
<i>dimensions</i>	50, 50, 50	50, 50, 50
<i>(x, y, z)</i>		
<i>Center</i>	101.542,	100.690,
<i>coordinates</i>	111.401,	107.895,
<i>(x, y, z)</i>	113.654	108.050
<i>Search algorithm</i>	Iterated	Iterated
	Local Search	Local Search
<i>Exhaustiveness</i>	20	20
<i>num_modes</i>	15	15
<i>energy_range</i>	5	5
<i>Seed</i>	42	42
<i>CPU</i>	5	5

Table 2: Docking parameters

Results

The binding energies (ΔG) and inhibition constants (K_i) of PET nanoplastics to SGLT1 and PePT1 proteins, obtained from molecular docking, are summarized in Table 3. The inhibition constant was calculated at 37°C (assumed body temperature) using Equation 1:

$$\Delta G = RT \ln(K_i) \quad (1)$$

- R: Ideal gas constant
- ΔG : Binding energy
- T: Absolute temperature

<i>Protein</i>	<i>Binding energy</i>	<i>Ki value (Molarity)</i>	<i>Ki Value (Nanomolar/Micromolar)</i>
SGLT1	-9.8	1.23×10^{-7} M	123 nM
PePT1	-7.4	5.96×10^{-6} M	5.96 μ M

Table 3: Docking results

Upon examining the data in Table 3, PET nanoplastics bind to SGLT1 with significantly stronger affinity compared to PePT1. Considering similar carrier inhibitor studies in the literature, the -9.8 kcal/mol value obtained for SGLT1 indicates a high binding strength. In contrast, the -7.4 kcal/mol value obtained for PePT1 falls within a range commonly observed in docking studies, representing moderate binding affinity. For example, in a study identifying potential antiviral flavonoids against SARS-CoV-2, a ligand binding to the protein with -7.26 kcal/mol was interpreted as strong binding (Rakshit et al., 2022).

In this context, the calculated -7.4 kcal/mol binding energy for PePT1 indicates that PET nanoplastics can establish a strong

and biologically relevant interaction with PePT1, but this interaction is weaker compared to the -9.8 kcal/mol value determined for SGLT1. This thermodynamic difference is reflected in the inhibition constant (K_i) values: the 123 nM value obtained for SGLT1 indicates approximately 48-fold stronger inhibitory potential than the 5.96 μ M calculated for PePT1. This nanomolar affinity level demonstrates that the potential of PET nanoplastics to inhibit SGLT1 is higher than for PePT1.

1. SGLT1-PET Interaction

The molecular docking results detailing the bonds formed by the ligand in the active site of the SGLT1 protein and the interacting amino acid residues are summarized in Table 4 and Figure 8. The PET oligomer was observed to occupy the Extracellular Entry Region, which is critical for substrate transport in SGLT1 (Figures 10-A and 11-A).

Conventional hydrogen bonds played a key role in stabilizing the interactions between the ligand and SGLT1. In particular, bonds formed with residues known to participate in the carrier mechanism, such as W291, N363, and Q457, supported the stabilization of the oligomer within the binding pocket. Additionally, π - π interactions with F101, Y290, and F453, as well as multiple alkyl/ π -alkyl interactions, indicated that SGLT1 binding is largely hydrophobic in nature (Table 4, Figure 8).

<i>Interaction Types</i>	<i>Amino Acids</i>
Conventional	
Hydrogen Bond (Figure 10A)	W291, N363, Q457
Carbon-Hydrogen Bond	F453, D454
π-π Interactions	F101, Y290, F453
Alkyl/π-Alkyl Interactions	H83, A93, 198, A160, V359, Y526
	N78, G82, G86, L87, T90, E102, A105, D273, M283, K321, T362, G450, Q451, 1456, T460
van der Waals Interactions	
Unfavorable (Acceptor-Acceptor)	T287

Table 4: Types of molecular interactions between the SGLT1 protein and the ligand and the participating amino acid residues

2. PePT1-PET Interaction

The most stable binding conformation of the PET oligomer with the PePT1 protein and the detailed interaction profile are presented in Table 5 and Figure 9. The PET oligomer was observed to occupy the Extracellular Entry Region critical for substrate transport, similarly to SGLT1 (Figures 10-B and 11-B). Unlike SGLT1, strong electrostatic interactions were observed in PePT1-ligand binding. Notably, a π -cation interaction with residue R27 and a π -sulfur interaction with residue C63 were detected. These interactions indicate that the PePT1 binding pocket contains more charged and sulfur-containing residues

compared to SGLT1, allowing the PET oligomer to stabilize this pocket through a distinct binding strategy. Strong hydrogen bonds with residues S599 and K140 further contributed to the stabilization.

<i>Interaction Types</i>	<i>Amino Acids</i>
Conventional Hydrogen Bond (Figure 10B)	R27, K140, S599, L623
Carbon-Hydrogen Bond	Y64
π-Sulfur Interaction	C63
π-π Interactions	W294
Alkyl / π-Alkyl Interactions	I170, L603, W622, L623, V626
van der Waals Interactions	Y30, Y31, P67, F166, N171, L624, A627

Table 5: Types of molecular interactions between the PePT1 protein and the ligand and the participating amino acid residues

Figure 9: 2D map of PET-PePT1 interactions.

Figure 8: 2D map of PET-SGLT1 interactions.

Conclusion and Discussion

The findings from molecular docking analyses demonstrate that PET nanoplastics can interact directly and with strong affinity with the human intestinal transporters SGLT1 and PePT1, which are responsible for nutrient absorption. The obtained binding energies and inhibition constants indicate that PET oligomers exhibit marked selectivity and superior inhibitory potential toward SGLT1 compared to PePT1. The ΔG value calculated for SGLT1 was -9.8 kcal/mol with an inhibition constant of 123 nM, whereas for PePT1, ΔG was -7.4 kcal/mol with an inhibition constant of 5.96 μ M. This comparison indicates that PET nanoplastics have nanomolar-level efficacy on SGLT1, approximately 48-fold stronger affinity than for PePT1, demonstrating binding comparable to potent inhibitors reported in the

Figure 10: Hydrogen bond surface color maps for PET with SGLT1 (A) and PePT1 (B), showing hydrogen bond donors (pink) and acceptors (green).

Figure 11: 3D structures of SGLT1 (A) and PePT1 (B) with the ligand (turquoise-colored oligomer).

literature. Such high affinity and selectivity suggest that PET nanoplastics could inhibit glucose absorption and pose a critical risk to intestinal physiology.

The observed high inhibitory potential can be explained by the interaction mechanism of PET oligomers targeting critical binding residues on SGLT1. PET nanoplastics directly interact with key amino acid residues involved in glucose binding and recognition, such as Q457, F453, and I456. In particular, the strong conventional hydrogen bond with Q457 and the carbon-hydrogen bond with F453 occupy the glucose recognition site, supporting a competitive inhibition mechanism. Moreover, PET was observed to bind residues in the extracellular gate region (Q457, F453, F101, and I98), which play a critical role in initiating the transport cycle and conformational changes. Specifically, π - π and alkyl interactions with F101 and I98 indicate the potential of nanoplastics to sterically hinder gate movements or disrupt normal conformational cycling. This dual-action strategy (both substrate recognition and gate locking) suggests that PET nanoplastics are likely to inhibit SGLT1 glucose transport.

For PePT1, the PET oligomer interacted with key residues involved in peptide binding, such as R27, K140, L623, W622, V626, and N171. Conventional hydrogen bonds with R27, K140, and L623 indicate that the nanoplastic oligomer can occupy the binding pocket by mimicking natural di- and tripeptide substrates, thereby physically preventing substrate binding. This suggests a potential competitive inhibition mechanism for PePT1. Additionally, the carbon-hydrogen bond with Y64 and other interactions in this region are important, as Y64 is critical for stabilizing the protein during the inward-occluded conformational transition. Interactions with this residue suggest that PET may act as a substrate mimic, affecting the protein's conformational transition or disrupting its stabilization during the transport cycle. Collectively, these interactions reveal the potential of PET nanoplastics to interfere with PePT1-mediated peptide transport.

In conclusion, molecular docking results indicate that PET nanoplastics can establish significant interactions with both SGLT1 and PePT1 transporters, with notably higher affinity, selectivity, and inhibitory potential for SGLT1. Occupation of the substrate recognition site and simultaneous engagement of the extracellular gate in SGLT1 suggest a strong inhibitory effect on glucose transport. For PePT1, although interactions are weaker, competitive inhibition may still disrupt the transport cycle and peptide absorption. These findings highlight PET nanoplastics as a potential risk factor for impaired nutrient absorption via intestinal transporters, warranting further experimental validation of their biological effects.

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